

NDAC/LO/079

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Disc space requirements for Step 2/3

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The software for Step 2/3 (sphere reconstitution and adjustment of astrometric parameters) consists of three major program units:

SORT23: sort and prepare abscissae [interface program between the Great Circle Reduction (Step 1) and Step 2/3 proper]

ACCU23: accumulate normals for the set zero points and preadjust the astrometric parameters; resolve slit errors

SOLV23: solve normals for the set zero points and global parameters

The last two programs are run alternately until the corrections become negligible.

The size estimates below are based on the following assumptions:

- total number of programme stars $\leq 120,000$
- total number of sets ≤ 2500 (16 sets/week for 3.0 years)
- number of abscissae per set: average = 2000, maximum = 2500

SORT23

For efficient sorting, the whole input file with abscissae from Step 1 must be on a direct access disc file. The sequential output (sorted abscissae) can be written directly on tape however. The simplest file structure is one record per set, which must then be dimensioned for the maximum number of abscissae in a set (2500). Content of one record (one set):

```

INTEGER*4  idset, nstar, idstar(2500)
REAL*4     sdabsc(2500)
REAL*8     absc(2500)

READ(lu, REC=irec) idset, nstar, idstar, absc, sdabsc

```

Thus 40,008 bytes/set => 100 Mb. Using a more efficient structure (with an index table) could reduce the file to 80 Mb, but this hardly seems worth while in view of the more severe requirements for ACCU23 (see below). No other significant files are used by this program, and the program itself is <1 Mb.

ACCU23/SOLV23

The accumulation and solution programs are treated together, since they operate on the same files.

Observation file: this contains the abscissae sorted according to objects. The average number of abscissae per star is given by (no. of sets) $\times$ (no. of abscissae per set) / (total no. of stars) = $2100 \times 2000 / 120000 = 35$. The file is unformatted sequential, with the record format (one star):

```

INTEGER*4  idstar, nobs, idset(maxobs)
REAL*4     sdabsc(maxobs)
REAL*8     absc(maxobs)

READ(lu) idstar, nobs, (idset(j), absc(j), sdabsc(j), j=1,nobs)

```

where `maxobs` is the maximum number of observations (abscissae) per star (say, 200). The average record size is thus $8 + 35 \times 16$ bytes = 568 bytes and the whole observation file is $120,000 \times 568 = 69$ Mb.

Object catalogue: this is a direct access unformatted file with one record per programme star. The current record format is (one star):

```

INTEGER*4  idstar
REAL*8-   temp(35)   REAL*4
DOUBLE*8  opar(40)   REAL*8

```

```

READ(lu, REC=irec) idstar, (opar(i), i=3,6), (temp(i), i=1,35)

```

Thus 176 bytes/star => 22 Mb.

Normal equations: the upper-diagonal part of the normals are stored in blocks whose size are determined by the available primary memory. With a reasonable blocklength the blocking efficiency should be about 90%. The maximum number of unknowns is 2600 (allowing for at most 100 global parameters) and all elements are REAL*8. The maximum size is then $\frac{1}{2} \times 2600^2 / 0.9 \times 8$ bytes = 30 Mb.

RGC catalogue: this contains 11 numbers (REAL*8) per set, thus a total of 0.22 Mb. This is actually doubled in practice, because it is both on a permanent disc file and in virtual memory.

Other files: files containing the global parameters and their covariances (0.04 Mb), blocking information, status and log files are small (total < 1 Mb). The programs (source and compiled) take another Mb.

SUMMARY

Allowing a 10% margin on the estimates above plus 10 Mb for overhead we arrive at the following requirements -

```

for SORT23:          120 Mb
for ACCU23/SOLV23:  146 Mb

```

All disc space used by SORT23 can be freed after the sorted data have been stored on tape.